

70. Agroforestry and "simplification" of the CAP

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EURAF is an NGO, based in Montpellier and Brussels (Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](#)). It aims "to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms". It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries. See other Policy Briefings [here](#).

"The one thing 'simplification' of the CAP is not is 'simple' ". Competence hearing, Phil Hogan, Member designate of the EC in charge of Agriculture and Rural Development, [2 October 2014](#),

Summary

Policy Briefing #70 v2 considers the impact of the removal of the GAEC8 landscape feature area targets by the 14/5/24 CAP Simplification Regulation (2024/1468). In principle, the replacement of the "stick" approach in the original GAEC8, with the "carrot" of additional eco-scheme funding was commendable. However, broad-brush country-level statistics (R.34, R14.4, I.21) cannot demonstrate that the carrot is working. The principle of "collect data once but use many times" could demonstrate an effect, but cannot happen until MS follow the guidance of the Strategic Dialogue for Agriculture and "prioritise and work towards a transparent data governance model with clear rules on data ownership, interoperability and ethical use".

Almost 20 years after entry into force of the EU INSPIRE Directive (2007/2/EC), many Member States or regions are still withholding access to IACS parcel-level data on policy measures and indicators. This geospatial data is needed to prove the effectiveness, or not, of specific interventions. The carrot of small eco-scheme payments for woody landscape features is unlikely to be sufficient at a time when some MS still refer to landscape feature trees as "unproductive" and prohibit farmers from feeding their branches to livestock!

Alternative sources of finance are crucial and the role of productive woody landscape features in carbon-farming will soon become vital for farmers throughout Europe, especially when combined with price-premia for their biodiversity benefits. This optimistic future should be possible with a new, data-driven, and low-bureaucracy approach to CAP simplification.

EURAF has submitted a proposal to DGAGRI showing how CAP ecoschemes, investment measures and agri-environment measures can be combined and simplified as a "starter pack" to help establish a voluntarily-certified agroforestry carbon farming scheme in all Member States.

The final section gives a list of 19 conclusions and recommendations related to simplification of the CAP and related legislation.

1. Introduction

EURAF Policy Briefing #70 is an input to the CAP Network Thematic Group on "Simplification of the CAP" ([link](#)). It responds to the Commission Staff Working Document "*Simplification measures for farmers*" ([SWD 2024 360 final](#)) and Regulation [2024/1468](#) on "amending Regulations (EU) 2021/2115 and (EU) 2021/2116 as regards good agricultural and environmental condition standards, schemes for climate, environment and animal welfare, amendments to CAP Strategic Plans, review of CAP Strategic Plans and exemptions from controls and penalties". It builds on the EURAF *Brno Agroforestry Declaration* ([31.5.24](#)), *Governance and performance of the CAP - the role of agroforestry* ([v2 28.10.24](#)) and *Agroforestry futures in the EU*" ([v2 25.2.25](#)), and a number of Policy Briefings (see [EURAF website](#)).

It also notes that there will be a second CAP Simplification Package published in Q2 2025 and another simplification package in Q4 which will consider the implications for agriculture of legislation outside the CAP.

The EURAF *Agroforestry Futures* document welcomed many aspects of the Commission's *Vision for Agriculture and Food*, including: the new "EU Observatory on Farmland" ([link](#)), the "Farm Sustainability Compass" ([link](#)),

"Nature Credits" and a "Toolbox of tailored measures to reduce emissions" ([link](#)). But **further simplification** of both measures and metrics are needed:

- For **measures**, EURAF proposes an "[agroforestry carbon-farming starter package](#)" which integrates existing eco-scheme (yr0), investment (yr1) and agri-environment measures (yr2-5) as a precursor to adoption of agroforestry into voluntary carbon farming certification schemes;
- For **metrics**, EURAF welcomes the principle of "*collecting data once and using multiple times*", and has long argued that much of the information requested from farmers and land managers can be made available by better use of existing data - particularly from IACS-LPIS systems (see [Policy Briefing #69](#)):

2. DGAGRI Vision and Initiatives

2.1 Abolition of GAEC 8 Targets in the Simplification Regulation (the "stick")

One of the most important simplifications in the March 2024 Regulation ([2024/1468](#)) was the removal of the requirement for arable farmers (above 10 ha and with less than 75% permanent pasture) to maintain a threshold area of 3%-4% landscape features and non-productive areas. To replace this "*stick*", the CAP SP Regulation was amended (see box below) to oblige Member States to provide additional support, through an eco-scheme for the maintenance of non productive areas and/or the establishment of new landscape features on arable land. Member States were obliged to apply this change from claim year 2025 at the latest.

(3) in Article 31, the following paragraph 1a is inserted:

'1a. As a part of the **eco-schemes** referred to in paragraph 1, Member States shall establish and provide support for schemes covering practices for the maintenance of non-productive areas, such as land lying fallow, and for the establishment of new landscape features, on arable land. These schemes shall be voluntary for active farmers and groups of active farmers.';

Commission Implementing Regulation [2024/1962](#) (18.7.24), clarified the reporting requirements, following this change: i.e. "*to enable the Commission to monitor and evaluate these eco-schemes, given the importance of the contribution of such practices to the specific objective related to biodiversity set out in Article 6(1), point (f), of Regulation (EU) 2021/2115¹, it should be provided that Member States are to report data on the number of eligible hectares paid for these practices. To facilitate an evaluation of the different practices covered by these eco-schemes, the data should be provided separately for **eco-schemes covering non-productive areas** and for **eco-schemes establishing new landscape features, on arable land**".*

It remains to be seen whether this recommendation has been implemented by all Member States in their updated CAP Strategic Plans, but it flags up a potential flaw with the PMEF Result Indicator (R.34) which is titled "*share of utilised agricultural area under supported commitments for management landscape features, including hedgerows and trees*" - since the detailed guidance for this indicator ([R.34](#)) includes a wide range of interventions, including sectoral interventions such as "restructuring and conversion of vineyards". For Indicator R.34, Member States need to record details of new "**landscape features under supported commitment**": meaning only those areas receiving direct financial support from the CAP"².

A second indicator which relates to Landscape Features is [R.17](#), which is titled "afforested land". There are four components to this: 17.1 Afforested area, 17.2 Restored area, 17.3 Agroforestry area and 17.4 Woody landscape features created.³ However, targets and achievements for these sub-indicators are not yet reported through the DGAGRI Measures Portal.

The third relevant indicator is I.21 ("Agricultural land covered with landscape features"), which records the total area of landscape features, whether under agricultural management agreements or not. This is currently only available at NUTS 3 (province) level: based on LUCAS data from the [JRC](#), or for woody landscape features from Copernicus data provided by the [EEA](#). JRC estimated that the total area landscape features is around 5.6% of EU farmlands, and the EEA calculated that woody landscape features alone cover around 5% of UAA. It is possible that more complete recording of existing landscape features would have achieved the threshold of 3%-4% UAA, and avoided the need for this "simplification". Nevertheless, the Staff Working Document ([Dec 2024](#)) estimated

¹ The CAP Strategic Plan Regulation -- aka the "CAP Basic Act".

² Note that the NRR incorrectly includes "fallow land" as a landscape feature.

³ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/17751WIQMFuKLRynRocNK1dGNma-K1s1eS2weZWl0g2o/edit?gid=0#gid=0>

that removing the GAEC8 threshold would save €930 million in additional income or avoided income loss, corresponding to a 1.5% increase in gross margin for the impacted farms. It is hard to have confidence in this estimate, given the poor availability of data on R.34, R.17.4 or I.21 at farm or parcel level⁴.

The Horizon-Europe DigitAF Project offers an alternative method using Copernicus tree-cover-density and Corine grassland/cropland categories at 100x100m pixel resolution (EURAF [Policy Briefing #26](#)). This “tree-desert” map [is also available](#) at NUTS3 level. Additional analysis using IACS/ LPIS data is needed at national level to quantify landscape features at **farm-scale**. This level of resolution is needed to support future CAP Pillar II “payment by results” schemes, and to link to carbon-farming certification.

“High Diversity Landscape Feature” targets (10%) were removed from the NRR during the co-legislation process, and the 4% target for GAEC 8 (landscape feature area) was removed from the CAP through the Simplification Regulation ([link](#)), however the simplification proposals also contained a commitment for all MS to ensure that Article 31 ecoschemes support the maintenance and establishment of landscape features.⁵

Use of the term “[non-productive trees](#)” in the Biodiversity Strategy and the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) has caused great confusion. The [final approved text](#) of the NRR improved this, but MS should take the opportunity to ensure that the rules for collecting data on "High Diversity Landscape Features (HDLF) in the NRR" are the same as "Landscape Features" (CAP GAEC-8). Differences are currently small. HDLF measurements should not include “temporary fallow” since, from the time of the Greening Regulation this has been viewed as a “non productive area” rather than a “landscape feature”. Following a commitment in Article 11 of the NRR, the Commission is working on new guidelines that member states can use for the collection of more detailed landscape feature data. The Commission, EEA and JRC have a role to support these improvements, particularly in reinforcing the LPIS system, which is the only feasible source of this data at a farm-scale ([link](#)).

Recommendation 1. Estimated savings to arable farmers by removing the GAEC8 area-thresholds have been overestimated in the Staff Working Document since landscape features and agroforestry systems can provide a means of increasing biodiversity and landscape value, while maintaining agricultural production. Landscape features should NOT be regarded as “non-productive areas” and the revised wording in the Implementing Regulation [2024/1468](#) is more correct than in the Basic Act.

⁴ In the CAP 2007-2013 this data was recorded in the Ecological Focus Area Layer of national GSAA/LPIS systems, and coordinated by the JRC MARS Unit as part of the collection of “Greening” data. In current CAP this central coordination of methodologies appears to have been abandoned or “simplified”.

⁵ Press release [15.3.2024](#). “**GAEC 8 on non-productive features**: EU farmers will have to maintain existing landscape features on their land but will no longer be obliged to dedicate a minimum part of their arable land to non-productive areas, such as fallow land. Instead, they may choose, **on a voluntary basis**, to keep a share of their arable land non-productive - or establish new landscape features (such as hedges or trees) - and thereby receive additional financial support via an **eco-scheme that all Member States will have to offer in their CAP Strategic Plans**. All EU farmers will be incentivised to maintain non-productive areas beneficial for biodiversity without fearing loss of income”. [COM 2024 139](#) Article 1 confirms that in Article 31 of Regulation 2021/2115), the following paragraph 1a is inserted: ‘As a part of the eco-schemes referred to in paragraph 1, Member States **shall** establish and provide support for schemes covering practices for the maintenance of non-productive areas, such as land lying fallow, **and for the establishment of new landscape features, on arable land**. These schemes shall be voluntary for active farmers and groups of active farmers.’ This amendment is also included in the Council’s agreed text.

2.2 New eco-schemes on landscape features introduced by Member States (the “carrot”)

EURAF summarised the definitions and implementation of GAEC 8 landscape features in [Policy Briefing #21](#) (30.1.23). The rules may have changed in later updates of the CAP Strategic Plans but as of 30.1.23 there were a number of Member States which did not recognise any or many landscape features (Table 1). It may be hard for these Member States (FI, SE, CY, DK, MT, SE) to implement a new eco scheme to support landscape features, if the features themselves are not recognised.

Table 1: Elements of Landscape Features and Non-Productive Areas (including numbers of sub-elements) selected in the CAP Strategic Plans of Member States (January 2023).

CAP-M	Landscape feature and non productive area	AT	BEF	BEW	BG	CY	CZ	DE	DK	EE	EL	ES	FI	FR	HU	HR	IE	IT	LT	LU	LV	MT	NL	PL	PT	RO	SE	SK	SI	Sum
B151	Fallow Land	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	3						30
B152	Hedges or woody strips	1	1	1	1			1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	20
B152	Trees in Line		1	1	1		1	1		1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1		1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	21
B152	Trees in Groups/ Copses	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	24
B152	Isolated Trees		1	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	19
B153	Buffer Strips	1	1	1	1			1									1	1			1	1	1			1	1	1	13	
B153	Field Margins (# types)		1	3	1	2	7	1	1	1		1		1	2		7	1	1	4	1		4		1	1	2	1	44	
B153	Forest Edge Strips - non prod		1	1	1					1	1					1	1												7	
B154	Ditches			1			1			1	1			1		1	1	1	1		1		3	1	1	1			16	
B154	Streams									1												1	1						3	
B155	Small Ponds	1	1	1						1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1			1	15	
B155	Small Wetlands						1	1		1										1	1	1	1	1					8	
B156	Traditional Stone Walls	1					1		1	1	1	1		1		1	1	1			1	1						1	12	
B157	Cairns	1					1			1	1								1	1	1					1			8	
B158	Terraces					1	1			1	1			1								1						y	7	
B159	Cultural Features	1		5				1	1	1	1	1		1		1							1						13	
B160	Others			1			2	1	1			2						1	1				4	1	1		-		15	
B161	Cover or catch crops (7% option)		-	-			1	-	-	-	-			1	1				-				-	-					3	
B162	N-Fixing Crops (7% option)		-	-			1			1	-	-		1	1				-				-	-					4	
	Total elements / sub-elements active	8	8	19	8	4	18	11	6	11	13	14	1	11	12	8	16	12	8	11	11	6	21	9	10	8	5	6	7	282
	4% Option	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	y	28
	3% Option	y		y	y			y	y	y	y			y						y	y		y		y				12	
	7% Option		y	y	y	y	y			y	y	y	y	y	y					y			y	y	y	y	y	y	16	
	LULUCF Regulation - threshold of "forest land" (ha)	0.05	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.3	0.05	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.3	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.1	1	0.5	0.1	1	0.25	0.5	0.3	0.25	
	Strategic Plan - max LF copse/grove size (ha)	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	-	?	0.2	?	?	?	0.3	-	0.5	0.5	?	-	0.3		0.3	0.5	-	1.5	0.5	0.5	0.9	-	?	0.5	
	Details of hedge width and permitted gaps?	y	y	y	y			y		y		y		y	y	y			y	y	y		y		y				15	
	Details of permitted crown size of trees in line?		y	y	y					y				y		y				y			y	y	y	y			y	13
	Details of crown size of isolated trees?		y	y	y									y	y	y				y			y	y					y	8

RED shows where the definition of "copse/grove" on agricultural land differs from the national definition the minimum size threshold for a forest block. In many countries the size threshold is not given or copses/groves are not recognised as Landscape Features

A search of the [Catalogue of CAP Interventions](#) revealed 174 eco-schemes in all MS, but only 6 of these mentioned “landscape” - hence it is hard to ascertain whether MS have indeed included new ecoschemes to support landscape features, as required in the Simplification Regulation. The six ecoschemes which mention landscape are:

- EL "Improvement of agroforestry ecosystems rich in landscape elements" (PI1-31.5)
- EL “Protection of landscapes and farming systems of high environmental importance”
- IT “Safeguarding olive trees of particular landscape value” (PD 05 - ES 3)
- LT “Maintenance of landscape features” (TI05eko1.5)
- LV “Creation or maintenance of landscape features (TM4.3)
- RO “Maintenance of non-productive areas and/or establishment of new landscape features on arable land” (PD-28)

A total of 75 Interventions (mainly Eco-scheme and ENVCLIM codes) were reported as contributing to Result Indicator 34 (“share of UAA under supported commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows and trees”), although these included only 24 Member States⁶. **In most cases the eco-schemes were very general in nature and did not mention landscape features, or only one type of landscape feature, like wildflower strips.** Some interventions were attributed to up to 20 Result Indicators, and no percent contribution is recorded in the current database (as it was in previous CAP periods). Greater reliance must therefore be placed on Result Indicator 17.4, but data on this is not yet available from MS.

Only two **R34 interventions mentioned “trees”**: IT (SRA25-ENVCLIM) and PL “Conservation of orchards of traditional varieties of fruit trees (I 8.4. - ENVCLIM). Furthermore, only two R34 interventions mentioned “wood” PL (I8.8 Afforestation and woodland premiums and agroforestry systems ENVCLIM) and BE-FL(3.9 - Management agreements for the maintenance of woody small landscape features) .

⁶ AT(31-05), BE-W(143), BG(I.B.2), CZ(05.31), DE(DZ-0401,DZ-0403), DK(9), EE(ÖK4,ÖK3), EL(PI1-31.10, PI1-31.8, PI1-31.5, PI1-31.3, PI1-31.2, PI1-31.7), ES (1PD31001801V1, 1PD31001802V1, 1PD31001809V1), FR (31.01), HR (31.03), HU (DP17_G01_ECOS_16), IE (51ECO), LT(TI05eko1.6, TI05eko1.7, TI05eko1.5), LU(1.02.513), LV (TM4.3), MT (DP ECO-NPE), NL(L1.31), PL(I 4.7, I 4.1), PT(A.3.6), RO(PD-28), SE(BL0M), SI(INP8.12), SK(31.1)

The revised Implementing Regulation ([2024/1962](#)) indicates that MS should record the number of hectares assisted by eco-schemes covering non-productive areas **separately** from those establishing new landscape features, on arable land”. This split is not available on the CAP [Result Indicators Dashboard](#), but looking at the combined non-productive areas and landscape %UAA targets (Table 2) there appear to be four strategies:

- decrease in area planned or mistaken data (BG, RO)
- no-change in areas planned (BE-F, CY, CZ, DK, EE, FI, FR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, MT, PT, ES)
- modest increase in area planned (HR, LV, NL, SL, SE)
- large increase in area planned (AT, BE-W, DE, EL, PL, SK)

Table 2: Planned area of CAP Result Indicator 34 “Share of UAA under supported commitments for managing landscape features, including hedgerows and trees (%) Note that R.34 measures the share of overall UAA, not just arable land.

Member State	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	Change
Austria	7.5	7.7	8.3	8.3	8.1	“+”
Belgium-Flanders	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0
Belgium-Wallonia	<0.5	1.6	1.9	2.1	2.4	“+”
Bulgaria	1.1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	“??”
Croatia	0.5	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	“+”
Cyprus	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3	0
Czechia	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0
Denmark	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9	0
Estonia	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Finland	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0
France	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Germany	3.0	3.6	3.9	4.0	4.2	“+”
Greece	13.8	13.3	14.8	14.8	16.8	“+”
Hungary	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Ireland	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.7	4.7	0
Italy	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Latvia	0.0	0.0	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	“+”
Lithuania	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9	0
Luxembourg	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	0
Malta	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0
Netherlands	3.0	3.6	3.6	3.6	3.6	“+”
Poland	<0.5	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	“+”
Portugal	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Romania	0.0	2.1	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	“??”
Slovakia	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.3	“+”
Slovenia	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.6	“+”
Spain	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	<0.5	0
Sweden	0.0	0.0	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	“+”

Recommendation 2. Four Member States (BE-F, FI, IT, CY) do not have any eco-schemes mapped against Result Indicator 34 (share of UAA under supported commitments to maintain landscape features) in the Catalogue of CAP Interventions, and only six MS have ecoschemes which specifically mention “landscape” in their titles. The mapping of eco-schemes to the “establishment of new ecoschemes on arable land” (as promised in 2024/1469) should be mapped by DGAGRI during 2025. Member States should check that the definitions of landscape features in their CAP Strategic Plans (EURAF [Policy Briefing #21](#)) match the way that these are recorded in their GSAA-LPIS systems.

2.3 A new EU Observatory on Farmland

The Vision for Agriculture and Food “In response to the European Parliament’s request⁷, and in line with the recommendation from the Strategic Dialogue, the European Commission will work towards launching an **EU Observatory on Farmland**. We will enhance transparency and cooperation in domains such as land transactions and transfers of land use rights, price trends and market behaviour; changes in land use, as well as loss of agricultural and natural land. The observatory will also help the Member States take informed decisions on the regulation of their farmland markets. Enhanced transparency of market developments and cooperation across the EU will make it easier to achieve legitimate interests of agricultural policy in compliance with single market freedoms”.

Recommendation 3. The proposed “EU Observatory on Farmland” is welcome, but it should be extended to contain information on forest land, thereby helping to clarify the huge errors in current identification of

⁷ European Parliament legislative resolution of 27 November 2024 on the joint text on the draft general budget of the European Union for the financial year 2025, P10TA(2024)0050.

forest and non-forest parcels illustrated in EURAF [Policy Briefing #15](#) and to integrate with national cadastres where possible.

2.4 The Farm Sustainability Compass

The Vision for Agriculture and Food indicates that “*The sustainability compass should act as a one-stop-shop that streamlines reporting and reduces administrative burdens for farmers, allowing them to monitor and record sustainability data only once. Secondly, it will support farmers in gradually adopting more sustainable practices and attracting new sources of financing. It will allow them to better measure and benchmark their sustainability performance and demonstrate their provision of ecosystem services through easier data sharing. Thirdly, improved measurement and reporting can help design public policies in a proportionate way. This voluntary system for on-farm sustainability assessments will be developed based on a bottom-up, participatory and ‘customer-driven’ approach*”

The Commission claims ([link](#)) to have changed the agricultural funding model from one of “compliance” to one of “performance”. However, the “Performance, Monitoring and Evaluation” metrics used for the current CAP mainly monitor spend or beneficiary numbers for measures which Member States “map” against the 10 Specific Objectives or 44 [Result](#) Indicators (on a 1-to-many basis), or 37 [Output](#) Indicators (on a 1:1 basis). For the first two, impressive indicators of spend can be produced, but double counting makes the data almost meaningless. A lot of indicators are framed with wording like R.14 (“share of UAA under supported commitments to reduce emissions or maintain or enhance carbon storage”) which don't have any quantitative link to emissions reduction..

There are also 49 "Impact Indicators". Data for these is available from a variety of sources but usually only at a national or regional scale, where they are unable to demonstrate the real “impact” of specific policies in the CAP. The [Impact Indicators](#) of most relevance to monitoring the impact of agroforestry - once they can be implemented at a farm scale - are:

- I.10 **Greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture**: uses national GHG emission calculations which vary greatly and are usually published only at a national level (NUTS 0). Only a few MS estimate the impact of woody vegetation outside forests separately.
- I.11 **Soil organic carbon in agricultural land** based on the LUCAS soil survey therefore not available at farm or parcel scale. Averaged to NUTS2
- I.12 **Sustainable production of renewable energy from agriculture and forestry** - agroforestry can contribute to this, but the indicator is published at national (NUTS 0) scale
- I.13 **Soil erosion by water** - scale is different between countries. Usually only published at regional scale (NUTS2)
- I.14 **Ammonia emissions from agriculture** - : based on manure management and fertilisation, but doesn't include the effect of ammonia sorption by agroforestry. Published only at national scale (NUTS 0)
- I.15 **Gross nutrient balance (N,P) on agricultural land (kg N & P/ha/yr)** - reports separately for the potential threat of nitrate and phosphorus on arable land and groundwater. Reports separately for cropland, grassland and permanent crops, but again availability is at the NUTS 0 level, and not for all MS.
- I.16 **Nitrates in groundwater** (percent of water stations with nitrate concentration over 50mg/l per Directive 91/676/EEC) - frequency of sampling and the density of the monitored stations vary from country to country, as does the number of sampling stations over the years. May be published at river basin level.
- I.17 **Water Exploitation Index** + (percent of water use over the renewable water resources available), only available at national level, or sometimes for river basins.
- I.19 **Increasing farmland bird populations**. Available at country (NUTS 0) level only. Species basket differs between countries, although a weighted EU basket exists. Most species will benefit from hedgerows and trees but other species (e.g. skylark and lapwing) prefer open land - therefore a less integrated index is needed.
- I.20b **Percent of species and habitats of community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends** only available at NUTS 2/3 level and relates to broad habitat types
- I.20a **Percentage of pollinator species of community interest related to agriculture with stable or increasing trends**: only available at NUTS 2/3 level
- I.21 **Agricultural land covered with landscape features**: but this is currently only available at NUTS 3 (province) level based on LUCAS data from the [JRC](#), or for woody landscape features based on Copernicus from the [EEA](#)

Recommendation 4. The proposed “Farm Sustainability Compass” is welcome but it seems similar to the Farm Sustainability Tool initially proposed as GAEC5 in the Commission’s first version of the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation. This was moved during dialogue to Farm Advisory Services - as Article 15-4(g)⁸

⁸ [advice on] sustainable management of nutrients, including at the latest as from 2024 the use of a Farm Sustainability Tool for Nutrients, which is any digital application that provides at least: (i) a balance of the main nutrients at field scale; (ii) the legal requirements on nutrients; (iii) soil data, based on available information and analyses; (iv) data from the integrated administration and control system (IACS) relevant for nutrient management;

of the SP Regulation ([2021/2115](#)), and has not been delivered by Member States. Greater importance should be given to the establishment of the Sustainability Compass than was given to its predecessor.

2.5 Nature Credits

The case for a move towards “Nature Credits” or “Environmental Payments” from basic area payments has been gathering some momentum in the EU. The Vision for Agriculture and Food ([25/2/25](#)) indicated that the Commission would complement the upcoming Carbon Farming component of the CRCF “with opportunities for nature credits - units of nature-positive actions, representing quantified and certified high-quality nature-positive outcomes. A number of existing schemes developed by commercial operators and ongoing pilot projects, both at EU and international level, show the important potential for such projects, on which further work can build”. The Strategic Dialogue on the Future of EU Agriculture ([29.8.24](#)) recommended “a system of targeted and result-oriented environmental payments [which] would offer farmers stable and predictable supplementary income, thus helping stabilize incomes, while delivering taxpayers clear value for their money”. It was clarified that “Rewarding payments should be conditioned on quantifiable outcomes that are measured by robust indicators. The funding level could be determined in conjunction with a dedicated benchmarking system for sustainable practices and outcomes at farm level. This framework should determine different levels of ambition for providing ecosystem services, with the respect of existing environmental and climate legislation as a baseline. Farmers who attain higher levels of ecosystem services as defined by the benchmarking framework could also be further rewarded”.

DGAGRI claims that the new CAP Delivery Model has moved from “compliance” to “performance” however the Performance Metrics used almost entirely relate to spend or beneficiary numbers rather than the impact of specific measures. Yes, there are 49 Impact Indicators but these are usually published at NUTS or NUTS1 level where the impact of specific measures which brought them about is unknown. There is no way of using these indicators to feed into the “Nature Credits” proposed for the next CAP (although interesting work is underway in some countries, such as with the Irish ACRES scheme). The drive for subsidiarity has brought a plethora of almost 1000 measures across ecoschemes, investment-measures and AECMs, but there is no method of classifying these in the DGAGRI database of interventions. There are also huge problems of double counting against Specific Objectives and Result Indicators.

Three new platforms: the [Result Indicators Dashboard](#), the [Catalogue of CAP Interventions](#), and the [Financial Allocation to CAP Specific Objectives](#) are provided by DGAGRI. They are timely and easy to use. However, they need further checks on the consistency of indicator codes used by Member States. For example, a number of measures dealing with agroforestry are not attributed to the forestry/agroforestry planting code (R.17), nor to the forestry/agroforestry annual support code (O.16). Impact Indicators should be recorded at a farm-scale, particularly CAP “[Impact Indicators](#)”. For this to happen, Member States should provide open access to their Land Parcel Identification Systems (LPIS) to researchers, and the long-promised Farm Sustainability Tool for nutrients (FaST) should be completed (qv). Recommendations in the Court of Auditors Special Report in 2022 on “Data in the Common Agricultural Policy” should be acted upon ([link](#)).

Recommendation 5. Opportunities for “Nature Credits” are attractive in principle, but it is difficult to establish objective methods which also reward “early-adopters”. Discussions in the Carbon Removals Expert Group are continuing on how to reward biodiversity co-benefits, but appropriate data is seldom available (EURAF Policy Briefing #66). Open access to geospatial data on vegetation and soils is needed, and better coordination of farm- and field-scale environmental indices across both agricultural (CAP) and environmental (NRR etc) legislation.

2.6 A toolbox of measures to reduce emissions

National reporting of GHG emissions has to go hand in hand with upcoming initiatives to monitor and report on carbon voluntary or statutory carbon-farming. Accounting methods for national reporting go back to the IPCC Good Practice Guide of Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry reporting ([2003](#)), and the importance of integrating national and farm-scale reporting of GHG emissions and land use change was emphasised by the European Environment Agency in their recent, “LULUCF Handbook ([2004](#))”. The measurements, modelling and “wall to wall” identification of parcels needed for calculation of the impact of agriculture and forestry on emissions underline the need for the Farm Sustainability Compass and open access to detailed information on land use, soil characteristics, and farming practices. Member States are slowly moving to a system of parcel-by-parcel emission reporting which will link up with DG CLIMA’s plans for a geospatial register of voluntary emissions certification by 2028, and potential introduction of an Agri Emissions Trading Scheme thereafter. Several Horizon research projects like [DigitAF](#), [LAMASUS](#), [Niva4CAP](#), [DIVINE](#), [SUPER-G CropCloud](#), [MEF4CAP](#), [AI4SoilHealth](#),

[Tools4CAP](#), [LIFE-Geocarbon](#), [PerceptiveSentinel](#), [ENVISION](#), Forest Navigator, Reforest, MARVIC, OrCASA, [Sen4CAP](#), [MRV4SOC](#), [LILAS4Soils](#), [CREDIBLE](#), [AgriCapture](#)

Recommendation 6. Publication by DGAGRI of its “Rough estimate of the climate change mitigation of CAP Strategic Plans over the 2023-2027 period ([Nov 2024](#)), but it is just a first step. The “rough estimate” notes GAEC-8 was expected to contribute around 0.9 million tonnes of CO₂e sequestration annually, predominantly stored in hedgerows and trees. The financial cost of this lost sequestration was not mentioned in the Staff Working Document on “Simplification”. EURAF published in [February 2024](#) a press release on the need for agroforestry to make up for the shortfall in carbon-sequestration demonstrated by Europe's forests. This called for an emergency planting programme of 11.2 Million ha of agroforestry before 2040. Much of this would have taken the form of woody landscape features covered by GAEC8.

2.7 The Farm Sustainability Data Network

The Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN) in the EU represents a significant evolution in agricultural data collection, building upon the existing Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN). It has many potential advantages for, a) sustainability assessment beyond economic factors to include environmental and social sustainability indicators, b) better-informed policy decisions related to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and other sustainability initiatives.; c) potential integration with other data sources like the Integrated Administrative Control System (IACS); d) allowing farmers to access reports that compare and benchmark their performance with similar farms, enabling them to identify areas for improvement, e) provide policymakers with robust data to analyze agricultural trends and assess the impact of policy measures, f) increases in transparency.

Against these advantages it must be admitted that: a) inclusion of sustainability indicators is increasing the administrative burden on farmers, despite efforts to streamline the process, b) data harmonisation has not been completed internationally and across a number of legislations, c) variations in data collection methodologies and interpretations may affect data comparability. d) costs of data collection, processing, and analysis are considerable, and e) sharing farm-level data raises concerns about data privacy and confidentiality. The FSDN was the product of extensive consultation, at which many participants said “*please do not base this on yet another questionnaire when most of the answers are already available from farmers returns to the IACS/GSAA or the Farm Structure Survey or forms on Areas of Natural Constraints or Herd Registers or Nitrate Directive forms or Organic Certification forms etc etc.*” Yet the final Annex to the Draft Implementing Regulation runs to 200 pages and seems to increase the questions asked of farmers from around 350 in the FADN to around 550 in the new form. Access to LPIS information is mentioned in the Annex but only for officials to manually check the answers which come from farmers, not to prefill their question forms as should have been the case.

Recommendation 7. EURAF [Policy Briefing #69](#) gives examples of the improvements in farm- and field-scale monitoring of agro-environmental indices which would provide much improved sustainability information and could potentially replace the need for the questionnaire-based FSDN.

2.8 JRC Classification of Farming Practices

The EU-JRC recently produced a “[Classification of Farming Practices](#)”, which has the potential to provide structure to the diverse list of the almost 1000 measures and practices supported by the CAP Strategic Plans of Member states in their ecoschemes (Article 31), investment measures (Article 73) and Agri-environmental Climate Measures (Article 70). Member States have vastly increased the complexity of their CAP Pillar I and Pillar II support programmes for agriculture and forestry, and additional legislative requirements (CAP, NRR, CRCF, FMR, SMD etc) have been added to the data gathering and comparison requirements. Greater use of the Classification of Farming Practices will facilitate improved comparisons between Member States and evaluation of the impacts of related agricultural measures. This is an excellent example of allowing maximum subsidiarity to Member States yet a “simplified” mechanism for lesson learning which can be shared with farmers.

Recommendation 8. There is no commitment to the “Data Governance Framework” in the DGAGRI Vision for Agriculture and Food, as there was in the Structural Dialogue. Anonymised open geospatial data is crucial for a wide range of purposes and legislations outside the CAP, and we note the good work done by the Horizon DigitAF project in producing an [LPIS Integrator](#) to link together data from MS whose data is both available and stable.

2.9 Rural Data Governance Framework

A clear recommendation from the *Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture* was the need for “robust data governance frameworks, and their proper implementation”, with the recommendation that “European Commission and Member States should prioritize and work towards a transparent data governance model with clear rules on data ownership, interoperability and ethical use, aiming at fair and secure use of data for the benefit of all, taking into account legal and ethical aspects”.

Box 1 shows the main mentions of “data” in the Strategic Dialogue ([link](#)), although surprising omissions were the Green Data4All Initiative and the EU Farm Sustainability Tool. The “**Data Governance Framework**” could be tackled as part of the GreenData4All Initiative (DGENV), but needs an inter-institutional approach.

BOX 1: Key mentions of “data” in the Strategic Dialogue for the Future of Agriculture

- *Agri-food value chain partners are key innovators and drivers of competitiveness. They are key contributors to maintaining lively rural communities and providing jobs. Digitalisation supports greater customer service, engagement, and information, and enables better demand forecasting and **sharing of data** for sustainability.*
- *Impact measurement and comparability of **farm-level data** will play an increasingly important role in the transition process. In that context, action will need to be taken to protect farmers’ rights and data.*
- *Farmers position in the value chain can be supported by capacity building in the form of access to technology, innovation, skills, **data, digital tools**, networking, and independent assistance*
- *The Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) should be further developed into the **Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN)** and implement methodologies to collect sustainability data at farm level.*
- *In the case of banks, to mobilise funding, they need to be sure that projects fit within policy sustainability targets and that the farmer or agri-food operator will be able to continue their activities for the coming years. To this end, **clear indicators and pathways** must be established and reflected in the prudential framework; at the same time, banks should be able to count on data protection regulations and the question of consent quality, **reliable data**, in line with ownership rights, that is sufficient to inform such benchmarks and risks analyses.*
- *The Commission should present, every three years and based on the benchmarking system, a ‘State of Agri-Food’ report taking stock of the progress achieved towards all three dimensions of the sustainability of EU agri-food systems and **identifying data gaps**.*
- *Animal welfare legislation requires the involvement of many actors: breeders, medicine providers, farmers, transporters, slaughterhouses, veterinarians, processors, retailers, consumers, NGOs, scientists etc. The challenge is to draw on **appropriate scientific data**, have the right transition periods, harmonise the rules, and provide farmers with the right tools and knowledge to take action*
- *Technologies for groundwater monitoring and **digital tools** to monitor the quantitative and qualitative status of water and soils are highly relevant. They should be developed in cooperation with the agricultural sector, including by the development of collaborative structures in order to **disclose the relevant data** to the relevant authorities and to the public. The European Commission should provide guidelines to Member States on the use of such instruments.*
- *As climate change and other economic, social, and geopolitical transformations impact competitive advantages, it is essential to design contingency planning to absorb and adapt to these structural changes. Therefore, based on **information and data provided by EU Member States**, the European Commission should conduct a strategic mapping of the structural shifts in agri-food production, as well as of key risks and vulnerabilities.*
- *Food systems are becoming increasingly digital. Today, in parts of Europe, crops, animals, or trucks are more and more monitored by smart sensors, satellites, drones, and machinery equipped with GPS and cameras. The result is a **wealth of data with unprecedented potential to support smarter decisions** by businesses or consumers, to trace food integrity, and to support public decision making by governments.*
- *The shift towards digitalization transcends mere technological advancements; it entails profound social, cultural, economic, and institutional changes. **Data utilisation can offer significant benefits** and support the benchmarking system and data exchange in the agrifood systems. It also raises concerns about fairness, quality and privacy. Hence, **robust data governance frameworks** and their proper implementation are essential.*
- *To promote digitalization in agri-food systems, the European Commission and Member States should prioritise and work towards a **transparent data governance model** with clear rules on data ownership, interoperability and ethical use, aiming at fair and secure use of data for the benefit of all, taking into account legal and ethical aspects.*
- *Incentives, e.g. within the CAP framework, are needed for the adoption of precision agriculture technologies, including IoT sensors, drones, AI, and satellite imagery, thereby improving resource efficiency and crop management. This must go hand in hand with sufficient funding for research development and **application of data acquisition**, interpretation and development of relevant algorithms and AI tools.*
- *Overall, **robust monitoring and evaluation** mechanisms need to be established to assess the impact of digitization initiatives in the agri-food sector. Data on adoption rates, productivity gains, **environmental outcomes**, and **socio-economic results** should be collected to inform future policy decisions.*

- *There is a need for more and better data on the sector's sustainability, to be integrated with **consistent metrics and clear indicators**, as well as for close monitoring and regular evaluations of agri-food actors' sustainability performance.*

Recommendation 9. There is no commitment to the "Data Governance Framework" in the DG AGRI Vision for Agriculture and Food, as there was in the Structural Dialogue. Anonymised open geospatial data is crucial for a wide range of purposes and legislations outside the CAP, and we note the good work done by the Horizon DigitAF project in producing an [LPIS Integrator](#) to link together data from MS whose data is both available and stable.

3. DGENV Vision and Initiatives

DG Environment has primary responsibility for large areas of legislation which affect agriculture and which have implications for "Simplification". These include the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and its accompanying targets, the Forestry Strategy 2030 and the Nature Restoration Regulation.

3.1 The Nature Restoration Regulation

Member States are obliged to publish draft plans by mid-2026, yet there are a wide range of agricultural and forestry metrics which need to be much better integrated with farm-scale CAP Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework. One example is that Member States are expected to devise national approaches to the monitoring of "high diversity landscape features" by August 2025, yet there is no clarity on how the unfortunate differences in definition between the DGAGRI and DGENV definitions of "landscape features" will be resolved. Clearly for the interests of farmers a single definition should be used, and this should tie in to the recording of landscape features in the Geospatial Aid Application, and clarification that their areas will continue to be eligible for area-based-payments, and potentially for agri-environment-climate payments.

Recommendation 10. EURAF [Policy Briefing #18](#) gives examples of the biodiversity indicators used for agriculture and forestry in the NRR, the urgent need for a single integrated set of agro-environmental-climate indicators to be used to monitor the impact of a range of legislation.

3.2 The Tree Billion Tree Target by 2030

Seven Member States (IE, NL, SE, FI, LU, FR, DE - except two Lander) now finance forestry and agroforestry through funds exclusively outside the CAP. They follow state aid rules defined in the Agricultural Block Exemption Regulation (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #19](#)). They may do this to "reduce bureaucracy"⁹, but it means that the Commission has little visibility on the "business as usual"¹⁰ tree-planting numbers, despite assuming that they are around 300 million/year.

Recommendation 11. The Commission's [MapMyTree](#) portal should report both the "state-funded, or business-as-usual" tree planting and the "additional" trees planted as part of the 3 Billion-Tree initiative. Since the LULUCF Regulation in 2018 Member States have an obligation to track the location of all tree planting causing land use change (i.e. "afforestation"), so creation of a unified "public" and "private" tree-planting database should be in their interest.

3.3 The Forest Monitoring Regulation and EU Deforestation Regulation

EURAF welcomed the draft Forest Monitoring Regulation (FMR) and supports improved monitoring of forests and trees-outside-forests, particularly for LULUCF and CRCF purposes. The indicators in Annex I are excellent. Those in Annex II need significant consultation with MS and industry. EURAF notes that there are large areas of grassland recorded in national LPIS systems which meet the FMR's unitary definition of "forest", yet are legally classified as grassland and are in receipt of CAP BISS payments. The legal indicator of "forest land" is provided by national forestry laws, national cadastres and LULUCF reporting. Imposing a single EU "forest" definition in the FMR will complicate LULUCF reporting (EURAF Policy Briefing #17). An alternative approach is to develop integrated rural cadastres which merge forest inventories and CAP-LPIS agricultural geostatistics, as has been done

⁹ Some MS use the ABER Regulation to enable 100% of actual planting costs to be reimbursed. Others use it to allow annual maintenance payments for longer periods than permitted in the CAP - e.g. up to 20 years in the case of Ireland.

¹⁰ Also expected to be 300 million trees per year but currently far short.

superbly in the Spanish SIGPAC system, partly to meet the needs of the LULUCF Regulation. EURAF has developed a pilot project proposal to support research on how to extend this integrated rural cadastre to other MS.

Recommendation 12. The definitions of "forest" used in both the FMR and EUDR should include the UNFCCC Marrakesh Accord definition used internationally for GHG reporting and contained in Annex II of the EU LULUCF Regulation. [Policy Briefing #15](#) gives the example of Extremadura in Spain, where the JRC map of forest cover, based on the FAO forest definition, overestimates the area of "forest" by a factor of five compared to the more detailed information available in the Spanish LPIS system (SIGPAC).

3.4 Biodiversity-Friendly Tree Planting Guidelines

These guidelines were promised in the Forestry Strategy and published by DGENV in [March 2023](#). The section on agroforestry was drafted with EURAF's assistance. The document supports authorities, foresters, farmers, landowners and civil society to better implement biodiversity-friendly afforestation, reforestation and tree-planting projects at the local level. However, as pointed out by the forestry sector when the Forestry Strategy was proposed, it may not be the job of the Commission to publish guidelines which have no statutory function and which duplicated a number of similar guidelines published by Member States, or internationally ([Forest Europe](#)) and through certification bodies like the [FSC](#) and the PEFC.

Recommendation 13. DGENV is urged to undertake a study of the uptake of its guidelines for biodiversity-friendly tree planting, and to update these guidelines on a periodic basis.

3.5 The GreenData4All Legislative Proposal

The Commission's GreenData4All initiative ([link](#)) will evaluate the implementation by Member States of EU INSPIRE Directive ([2007](#)). It hopes to assist Europe's green and digital transformation by updating EU rules on environmental geospatial data and on public access to environmental information. GreenData4All should enable greater sharing of data between the public & private sectors and with the general public, and "unlock the full benefits of data sharing for data-driven innovation and evidence-based decisions". It is very relevant to the sharing of the soils and land-use information needed for Carbon Removals certification and for LULUCF reporting of land use change. Details of the initiative, following a consultation in 2023 (ref) remain to be finalised.

Recommendation 14. DGENV is urged to continue with its "GreenData4All" but emphasising that this data is needed not just for environmental purposes but for monitoring of the effectiveness of interventions and perhaps "payment by results" It could be integrated with the DGAGRI initiative to "prioritise and work towards a transparent data governance model with clear rules on data ownership, interoperability and ethical use", mentioned in the Strategic Dialogue.

3.6 Soil Monitoring Directive

The Soil Monitoring Directive SMD ([COM2023-415](#)) requires the creation of "soil districts" throughout the territory of Member States. Soil districts should "constitute the basic governance units to manage soils and to take measures to comply with the requirements laid down in this Directive, in particular with regard to the monitoring and assessment of soil health" BUT the Directive indicates that there need not be more "districts" than the number of NUTS1 units, of which there are 92 in the EU. This is far too coarse a spatial division to be of use to the CRCF, or any other legislation requiring spatial land planning and management. The draft SMR expects MS to implement an enhanced LUCAS topsoil monitoring programme and to integrate with national databases of soil properties. EURAF is awaiting progress with parcel-scale recording of soil data in the Farm Sustainability (FaST) Platform from Member States by the end of 2024, as committed in the Sustainable Carbon Cycles Communication (see EURAF [Policy Briefing #25](#)).

Recommendation 15. The Farm Sustainability tool, or its successor the Farm Sustainability Compass are the logical place to store soils and fertiliser data, and urges the Commission to include these parcel-based initiatives in the final wording of the Soil Monitoring Directive.

4. DG CLIMA Vision and Initiatives

4.1. The Carbon Removals Certification Framework

The upcoming harmonisation of CRCF methodologies and verification rules, together with completion of the carbon farming parcel-based geospatial registry by 2028, will open the door for the launch of an AFOLU Emission

Trading System, and it is disappointing that this is not mentioned in the Vision. It will be needed for the possible extension of energy accounting to agriculture and forestry imports via the EU Carbon Borders Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM).

Long-term support for the livestock sector, mentioned in the DGAGRI Vision for agriculture and food, with an emphasis on traditional extensive grazing is welcome, but we note that most of these systems depend on silvopastoralism, and Member States have done little to support this historic practice in recent CAP programmes. EURAF’s Brno Declaration called for 2 million ha of new silvopastoral areas and greater support for the restoration of parkland systems. We also hope for an emphasis on delivering the Commission’s plans for 3 billion additional trees by 2030, including EURAF’s call for 8.6 million ha of new silvoarable areas. Carbon-farming certification is crucial to achieve these targets.

EURAF’s [Policy Briefing #8](#) suggests integrated CAP and carbon farming planning. Starting with CAP Pillar I Ecoschemes (Article 31) for planning and baseline sampling in year 0, followed by Pillar II Investment measures (Article 74) in year 1, and Pillar II AECM (Article 70) for annual maintenance support in years 2-5, and subsequent “adoption” into carbon-certification schemes in five-year tranches i.e. yrs 6-10, 11-15, 16-20 etc. Mapping and registration of trees outside forests (ToF) as “landscape features” could give guarantees of “permanence” for carbon-certification. [Policy Briefing #20](#) gives further suggestions and will be modified in 2024/25 as the Commission develops its Carbon Farming Delegated Act for the Carbon Removals Certification Framework. The concern to avoid a small amount of “**financial additionality**” should not stand in the way of the urgent need to get trees into the ground as fast as we possibly can: recognising that for at least the first five years they sequester practically no carbon. Currently, little support is available in the CAP. This should improve (Table 3).

Table 3: Measures in Member States which specifically refer to agroforestry. New measures are being developed in Austria and the Netherlands. France and Ireland have measures outside the CAP

MS	Article	Code	O.16 (total)	R.17 (total)	Measure
BE-FL	Art 70	3.7	€281,384		Management of agroforestry systems (boslandboussystemen)
CZ	Art 70	26.7	€1,357,200		Caring for an established agroforestry system
CZ	Art 73-74	42.73		€3,917,700	Establishment of an agroforestry system
DE	Art 31	DZ-0403 –			Maintaining agroforestry management on arable land and permanent grassland
EL	Art 31	P1-31.05 –		€66,564,568	Improvement of agroforestry ecosystems, rich in landscape elements
ES	Art 70	6502.2	€27,069,248		Maintenance of Forests and Agroforests
ES	Art 73-74	6881.1		€68,809,809	Non productive investments in afforestation and agroforestry systems
IT	Art 70	SRA28	€66,080,718	€66,080,718	Support for maintenance of forestation/afforestation and agroforestry systems
IT	Art 73/74	SRD05		€47,387,981	Forestation/afforestation and agroforestry systems on agricultural land
PL	Art 70	I.8.8			Afforestation and afforestation premiums and agroforestry schemes
PL	Art 73-74	I.10.13.		€5,998,785	Establishment of agroforestry systems
PT	Art 70	C.1.1.3			Agroforestry Mosaic (Attributed to O.14 and R.14, R31, R.33)
PT	Art 70	D.2.2			Management of the montado (agroforestry) by Results
PT	Art 73-74	C.3.2.2		€3,360,000	Setting up agroforestry systems
PT	Art 73-74	F.2.2		€300,000	Investment in the creation and regeneration of agroforestry systems
SK	Art 70	70.01	€2,932,150	€2,932,150	Protection and maintenance of trees within the established Agroforestry system
SK	Art 73-74	73.01		€2,932,150	Establishing an agroforestry system

Recommendation 16. Carbon farming certification should be planned in conjunction with CAP tree-planting support. The CAP can support initial planning and baseline soil sampling, together with initial years of tree planting. Carbon certification can provide long-term financial support in later years of the plantation, linked to regular monitoring and reporting.

4.2 The LULUCF and Effort Sharing Regulations

Member States were obliged to Indicate under the terms of the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation Article 120 on the modifications to the current CAP which would be needed to help them meet their 2030 LULUCF (-310 MtCO₂e) and Effort Sharing targets. DGCLIMA should publish these letters, since there is little evidence that MS have indeed modified their CAP Strategic Plans to better meet these targets or to improve their GHG accounting methods ([Court of Auditors, 2024](#)). As of 18.10.24, only 11 Member States had published final versions of their National Energy and Climate Plans and few of these had recognised the importance of agroforestry in meeting AFOLU emission reduction targets. France is a notable exception. DG CLIMA last year published guidance on “improving the contribution of land-use, forestry and agriculture to enhancing climate, energy and environment ambition” ([May 2023](#)) and their December 23 “[EU-wide assessment](#)” was a clear indication of the huge scale of the shortfall in emissions reduction.

The LULUCF Regulation ([2018/841](#)) was updated in 2023 ([2023/839](#)) to set ambitious EU and national targets. The amended Regulation has removed certain flexibilities from 2026 onwards, or made them dependent on the EU as a whole reaching its targets. The Regulation, in Annex II, also defines “forest land” using the Marrakesh Accord ([2021](#)) thresholds for block size, crown cover and tree height, consistent with reporting made by Member States to the UNFCCC upon which LULUCF compliance is assessed. The UNFCCC definition should have been used in the EU Forest Monitoring Regulation ([PB#15](#)) since compliance with UNFCCC and national laws are of primary importance. It was disappointing that the Communication on Europe’s 2040 climate target removed the 2035 land-sector neutrality commitment ([COM 2024 final](#)) present in the earlier proposals under the Green Deal and the February 2024 [Impact Assessment](#) EURAF issued a [press release](#) indicating that agroforestry could contribute 56 MtCO₂e by 2040 if a planting programme of 750 kha/yr starts in 2025. Member States are currently considering how to redirecting unspent rural development funds to support farmers, forest owners and SMEs which are affected by extreme weather events (a total amount of up to 600 million EUR), EURAF estimates that investing only 1% of such budgets per year in targeted agroforestation activities (e.g. establishment of new systems in areas most vulnerable to climate catastrophes) could contribute to accelerating progress on LULUCF targets - while also reducing the damage caused by extreme weather events by up to 50%. See v4 of EURAF [Briefing #17](#) ”Agroforestry and the LULUCF Regulation”.

Almost no information is available on agroforestry or forestry in these databases. There is no indication of the area of agricultural land where area support (BISS) is judged by inspectors to be ineligible because of tree-cover (including hedges and small copses), yet this "ineligibility" is one of the main factors dissuading farmers from engaging in agroforestry. Improved summary information is also needed on the small number of measures which directly support agroforestry (Table 1). They are only partially coded by MS using indicators for tree establishment/restoration (Result Indicator R.17) or annual tree-planting maintenance payments (Output Indicator O.16). Only 17 measures from a combined total of 948 in Articles 31 (ECO), 70 (AECM) and 73-74 (INVEST) specifically mention agroforestry (DigitAF Project [Deliverable 1.1](#)).

Recommendation 17. Close integration between methods and databases used by Member States for the calculation of national Greenhouse Gas Inventories with those to be used for farm-scale certification of carbon removals and emission reductions.

5. Other Directorates - role in potential “Simplification”

5.1 Directorate-General for Taxation and Customs Union (DG TAXUD)

DG TAXUD is responsible for the potential extension of the Carbon Borders Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) to forestry and agriculture. An Agri-ETS is a prerequisite to extending the CBAM ([2023/956](#)) to farming and forestry. The existing CBAM aims to ensure that imports have paid a price for the carbon emissions produced during their manufacturing. This makes the carbon cost of imports comparable to domestic production, safeguarding the EU’s climate goals. It will apply to specific goods like cement, iron and steel, aluminium, fertilisers, electricity, and hydrogen – industries that have high carbon emissions and are at risk of carbon leakage. It currently excludes forestry and agricultural imports, despite amendments suggested by [COMAGRI](#), and other views (e.g. [Allan Matthews 2022](#)). Before any surcharges can be placed on imports of food and agricultural produce it is likely that the EU will have to introduce a statutory carbon-pricing scheme for agriculture and forestry, such as currently under discussion ([Trinomics 2023](#)). This will need a national registry of agricultural and forestry parcels, as proposed in the Carbon Removals Certification Framework for 2018.

Recommendation 18. Extending the CBAM to agricultural and forestry products was a long term goal of the Agriculture Committee of the European Parliament. This gives another reason to introduce statutory carbon accounting in agriculture and forestry through a possible extension of the EU Emission Trading Scheme.

5.2 Directorate-General for Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Unions

DG FISMA has primary responsibility for the Sustainable Finance Initiative (SFI) ([2020/852](#)). This initiative relates to tree planting in the private sector, rather than “business as usual” tree planting supported by Member States. The SFI sets climate and environment criteria for activities which are classed as sustainable: including forestry and paludiculture. The Delegated Acts for Climate ([2021/2139](#)) and Environment ([2021/2178](#)) are important, as is the EU [Taxonomy Navigator](#). EURAF has submitted a technical proposal to include agroforestry in the SFI taxonomy (Policy Briefing [#28](#)) and is working on Policy Briefings for the other aspects of sustainability listed (“do no significant harm”) in the SFI, i.e.: adaptation - (Policy Briefing [#27](#)), water quantity and quality (Policy Briefing [#64](#)), pollution (Policy Briefing [#65](#)), biodiversity (Policy Briefing [#66](#)) and the circular economy

(Policy Briefing [#67](#)). Acceptance of agroforestry into the Sustainable Finance Initiative should facilitate its increased utilisation in Europe and will contribute to its uptake within the Carbon Removals Certification Framework ([link](#)).

Recommendation 19. DG FISMA should reintroduce sustainable agricultural practices in the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy and consider the recommendations of [EURAF Policy Briefing #28](#) for inclusion of agroforestry.

5. Conclusions & Recommendations

1. Estimated savings to arable farmers by removing the GAEC8 area-thresholds have been overestimated in the SWD since landscape features and agroforestry systems can provide a means of increasing biodiversity and landscape value, while maintaining agricultural production. ***Landscape features should NOT be regarded as “non-productive areas”*** and the revised wording in Regulation [2024/1468](#) is more correct than in the Basic Act.
2. Four Member States (BE-F, FI, IT, CY) do not have any eco-schemes mapped against Result Indicator 34 (share of UAA under supported commitments to maintain landscape features) in the Catalogue of CAP Interventions, and only six MS have ecoschemes which specifically mention “landscape” in their titles. The mapping of eco-schemes to the “establishment of new ecoschemes on arable land” (as promised in 2024/1469) should be mapped by DG AGRI during 2025. Member States should check that the definitions of landscape features in their CAP Strategic Plans (EURAF [Policy Briefing #21](#)) match the way that these are recorded in their GSAA-LPIS systems.
3. The proposed “EU Observatory on Farmland” is welcome, but it should be extended to contain information on forest land, thereby helping to ***clarify the huge errors in current identification of forest and non-forest parcels*** illustrated in EURAF [Policy Briefing #15](#) and to integrate with national cadastres where possible.
4. The proposed “Farm Sustainability Compass” is welcome but it seems similar to the Farm Sustainability Tool initially proposed as GAEC5 in the Commission’s first version of the CAP Strategic Plan Regulation. This was moved during trialogue to Farm Advisory Services - as Article 15-4(g)¹¹ of the SP Regulation ([2021/2115](#)), and has not been delivered by Member States. Greater importance should be given to the establishment of the Sustainability Compass than was given to its predecessor.
5. Opportunities for “Nature Credits” are attractive in principle, but it is difficult to establish objective methods which also reward “early-adopters”. Discussions in the Carbon Removals Expert Group are considering how to reward biodiversity co-benefits of carbon-farming, but appropriate data is seldom available (EURAF [Policy Briefing #66](#)). There is a crucial need for open access to geospatial data on vegetation and soils, and for better coordination of farm- and field-scale environmental indices across both agricultural (CAP) and environmental (NRR etc) legislation.
6. Publication by DG AGRI of its “Rough estimate of the climate change mitigation of CAP Strategic Plans over the 2023-2027 period ([Nov 2024](#)), but it is just a first step. The “rough estimate” notes GAEC-8 was expected to contribute around 0.9 million tonnes of CO₂e sequestration annually, predominantly stored in hedgerows and trees. The financial cost of this lost sequestration was not mentioned in the Staff Working Document on “Simplification”. EURAF published in [February 2024](#) a press release on the need for agroforestry to make up for the shortfall in carbon-sequestration demonstrated by Europe's forests. This called for an emergency planting programme of 11.2 Million ha of agroforestry before 2040. Much of this would have taken the form of woody landscape features covered by GAEC8.
7. EURAF [Policy Briefing #69](#) gives examples of the improvements in farm- and field-scale monitoring of agro-environmental indices which would provide much improved sustainability information and could potentially replace the need for the questionnaire-based FSDN.

¹¹ [advice on] sustainable management of nutrients, including at the latest as from 2024 the use of a Farm Sustainability Tool for Nutrients, which is any digital application that provides at least: (i) a balance of the main nutrients at field scale; (ii) the legal requirements on nutrients; (iii) soil data, based on available information and analyses; (iv) data from the integrated administration and control system (IACS) relevant for nutrient management;

8. The EU-JRC “Classification of Farming Practices” and its recent integration in the “[Catalogue of CAP interventions](#)” is welcome. The Classification will improve comparability between Member States of farming systems and interventions, and assist in the sharing of good practices.
9. There is no commitment to the "Data Governance Framework" in the DG AGRI Vision for Agriculture and Food, as there was in the Structural Dialogue. Anonymised open geospatial data is crucial for a wide range of purposes and legislations outside the CAP, and we note the good work done by the Horizon DigitAF project in producing an [LPIS Integrator](#) to link together data from MS whose data is both available and stable.
10. EURAF [Policy Briefing #18](#) gives examples of the biodiversity indicators used for agriculture and forestry in the NRR, the urgent need for a single integrated set of agro-environmental-climate indicators to be used to monitor the impact of a range of legislation.
11. The Commission’s [MapMyTree](#) portal should report both the “state-funded, or business-as-usual” tree planting and the “additional” trees planted as part of the 3 Billion-Tree initiative. Since the LULUCF Regulation in 2018 Member States have an obligation to track the location of all tree planting causing land use change (i.e. “afforestation”), so creation of a **unified “public” and “private” tree-planting database** should be in their interest.
12. The definitions of "forest" used in both the FMR and EUDR should include the UNFCCC Marrakesh Accord definition used internationally for GHG reporting and contained in Annex II of the EU LULUCF Regulation. [Policy Briefing #15](#) gives the example of Extremadura in Spain, where the JRC map of forest cover, based on the FAO forest definition, overestimates the area of "forest" by a factor of five compared to the more detailed information available in the Spanish LPIS system (SIGPAC).
13. DG ENV is urged to undertake a study of the uptake of its guidelines for biodiversity-friendly tree planting, both with and without public subsidies, and to update these guidelines on a periodic basis.
14. DG ENV is urged to continue with its "GreenData4All" but emphasising that this data is needed not just for environmental purposes but for monitoring of the effectiveness of interventions and perhaps “payment by results”. It could be integrated with the DG AGRI initiative to "prioritise and work towards a transparent data governance model with clear rules on data ownership, interoperability and ethical use", mentioned in the *Strategic Dialogue*.
15. The Farm Sustainability tool, or its successor the Farm Sustainability Compass are the logical place to store soils and fertiliser data, and urges the Commission to include these parcel-based initiatives in the final wording of the *Soil Monitoring Directive*.
16. Carbon farming certification should be planned in conjunction with CAP tree-planting support. The CAP can support initial planning and baseline soil sampling, together with initial years of tree planting. Carbon certification can provide long-term financial support in later years of the plantation, linked to regular monitoring and reporting.
17. Close integration between methods and databases used by Member States for the calculation of national Greenhouse Gas Inventories with those to be used for farm-scale certification of carbon removals and emission reductions.
18. Extending the CBAM to agricultural and forestry products was a long term goal of the Agriculture Committee of the European Parliament. This gives another reason to introduce statutory carbon accounting in agriculture and forestry through a possible extension of the EU Emission Trading Scheme.
19. DG FISMA should reintroduce sustainable agricultural practices in the Sustainable Finance Taxonomy and consider the recommendations of [EURAF Policy Briefing #28](#) for inclusion of agroforestry.

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